

To Study the Impact of Arts Based Therapy on the Self Esteem of Clients Admitted in a Rehabilitation Centre for Substance and Behavioural Addictions

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Abstract

Background: Admitting and treating someone in a rehabilitation facility is one method of assisting them to overcome their drug dependence and acquire a healthy outlook and way of life. It gives them a more secure location to be in, away from drugs and associates or friends that use them. The rehabilitation centre has a scheduled schedule that allows programme participants to experience the advantages of having regular sleep and waking hours, exercise, regular meals, and introspection through engaging group and one-on-one sessions. The use of art in a therapeutic setting to achieve specific, personalised goals is known as arts-based therapy.

Aim: This study was carried out to evaluate the impact of Arts Based Therapy on the self-esteem of clients admitted in a rehabilitation centre for substance and behavioural addictions.

Methods and Materials: The participants in the group went through assessment by a psychiatrist, a proforma was filled to collect data. The diagnosis of comorbid psychiatric disorders was made according to the criteria in Diagnostic and Statistical Manual-5. 34 sessions of one hour duration at a frequency of two sessions in a week were conducted by ABT student. Out of which four hours were dedicated to administration of pre and post therapy scales and 30 sessions of ABT. The sessions were planned and recorded on Session Record Sheet (SRS).

Results: It was found that there was there were significant improvement in the Rosenberg self-esteem scale scores after ABT sessions. There was strong negative correlation between absenteeism due to alcohol and self-esteem scores indicating that there with improved self-esteem absenteeism at work place will reduce.

Conclusion: Considering the improvements in the scores of self-esteem and emotional regulation, Arts Based Therapy could be used widely in the treatment and rehabilitation of people having substance and behavioural addictions.

Keywords: Art Based Therapy, Self-Esteem, Rehabilitation Centre

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Introduction

Addictions to substances and behaviours have a significant impact on every aspect of the lives of those who suffer from them. The character of the issue is of recurrence. So these individuals are frequently accepted into rehabilitation facilities. They utilise tobacco, alcohol, and marijuana recreationally. Usually, it starts out with friends because of intrigue, experimenting, and peer pressure. Through frequent use, these substances build a tolerance that eventually results in dependency through greater frequency and amount of usage. Adverse life experiences often make substance use worse, progressing from infrequent to frequent to dangerous usage. Later, due to the unpleasant withdrawal symptoms after cessation, they find it difficult to stop using these substances [1,2].

Their lives start to include substance usage, which has a negative impact on their reputation, social life, finances, work, and academic performance. There is interpersonal tension when someone tries to discourage someone from doing drugs. They begin lying, spending carelessly, piling up debt, selling items, gambling, or stealing to fund their substance abuse, and some may wind themselves in legal trouble. Intoxication-related accidents happen frequently. Some people who are using drugs have behavioural issues that might cause conflict in relationships. All aspects of their lives are negatively impacted by substance misuse, and they frequently cannot escape this pattern on their own [3-5].

Admitting and treating someone in a rehabilitation facility is one method of assisting them to overcome their drug dependence and acquire a healthy outlook and way of life. It gives them a more secure

location to be in, away from drugs and associates or friends that use them. The rehabilitation centre has a scheduled schedule that allows programme participants to experience the advantages of having regular sleep and waking hours, exercise, regular meals, and introspection through engaging group and one-on-one sessions. Due to pressure from family members, the majority of patients enter rehabilitation facilities resentfully and with various levels of motivation and animosity [6-8].

The use of art in a therapeutic setting to achieve specific, personalised goals is known as arts-based therapy (ABT). It is based on the Subtle Energy Guide (SEG), which incorporates research from the fields of cognitive neuroscience, human development, and Indian psychology and ethics. ABT draws inspiration and employs techniques from the visual, dramatic, and musical arts. The arts so utilised contribute to the therapeutic role in a variety of ways, including artistic ability, experimenting with painting and sculpture through improvisation, building and tearing down metaphoric meaning, and situations that are beyond words [9-11]. This study was carried out to evaluate the impact of Arts Based Therapy on the self-esteem of clients admitted in a rehabilitation centre for substance and behavioural addictions

Methods and Materials**Eligibility criteria for participants**

17 men between the ages of 18 and 60 for intensive management of substance addiction or abuse and addictive behaviors admitted in the Deaddiction and Rehabilitation Centre. Patients who received sufficient treatment for

their withdrawal symptoms were added to the group.

Consent procedure

The participants' assent to participate in the ABT sessions was obtained after the consent form was read to them and explained in Hindi and the local tongue.

Logistical arrangements

ABT sessions were conducted on the outdoor terrace of the rehabilitation centre twice per week. The rehabilitation centre is required to supply the necessary art supplies and infrastructure.

Most commonly occurring therapeutic goals that I will work on:

- a) Group interactions
- b) Creative expression
- c) Building empathy, self esteem

1. Methods for doing needs assessment with the group:

- a) History taking and clinical assessment was done by a psychiatrist.
- b) Difficulties in emotional regulation scale (DERS)
- c) Rosenburg self-esteem scale

The scales were administered at the beginning of the study and at the end of the study.

Audio video recording of sessions was used to review the sessions and make observations of the participants.

Summary of the Arts Based Therapy interventions used:

Arts-based therapy refers to the application of art in a therapeutic environment to meet particular, individual aims (ABT). Its foundation is the Subtle Energy Guide (SEG), which draws on studies in the areas of cognitive neuroscience, human development, and Indian psychology and ethics. ABT uses techniques from the theatrical, musical, and visual arts as well as takes inspiration from them. The arts in this context are used to serve a therapeutic purpose in a number of

ways, including artistic skill, improvisational art form exploration, the construction and dismantling of metaphoric meaning, and experiences that are beyond language.

There is gradation in ABT:

Artistic skills in rhythms, voice, body, visual arts and group exercises.

Improvisations with each artistic skill, combination of various artistic skills, with props/ objects and in response to various inputs of the working group.

Metaphors through images, narratives and compositions.

Beyond meaning the silence, meditation, contemplation.

ABT practice, guided by SEG, manifests in graded artistic experiences.

The participants in the group went through assessment by a psychiatrist, a proforma was filled to collect data. The diagnosis of comorbid psychiatric disorders was made according to the criteria in Diagnostic and Statistical Manual-5. 34 sessions of one hour duration at a frequency of two sessions in a week were conducted by ABT student. Out of which four hours were dedicated to administration of pre and post therapy scales and 30 sessions of ABT. The sessions were planned and recorded on Session Record Sheet (SRS).

Results

Most of the study participants were in the age group of 21 to 30 years (8 patients). It was followed by age group of 31 to 40 years (5 patients). (table 1, graph 1). 5 patients were educated up to class 12. 4 patients were educated up to class tenth. 3 patients didn't completed graduation. Only 2 patients were graduate. (table 2, graph 2). 7 patients were self-employed. 3 patients were farmers. 3 patients were in service. 4 patients were unemployed. (table 3). The most common cause of absenteeism in sessions was alcohol with 15 patients got absent due to alcohol.

(table 4). Of the 9 married men 6 reported at least 1 episode where wife left for her parents' home indicating the impact on marital life. (Table 5, graph 3). Friends influence was the most common self-reported reasons for substance use or relapse. (Graph 5). Craving was the most common self-reported withdrawal symptoms. (graph 6). 9 patients stayed for 1 months while 6 patients stayed for 2 months. (table 6). Applying paired t test there is statistically significant improvement in self-esteem scores after therapy.(table 7)

It was found that there was there were significant improvement in the Rosenberg self-esteem scale scores after ABT sessions. There was strong negative correlation between absenteeism due to alcohol and self-esteem scores indicating that there with improved self-esteem absenteeism at work place will reduce. There was reduction in mean DERS scores in all domains. There was a statistically significant reduction in Goals, impulse, strategies subscales and overall mean DERS scores after the therapy. This means that with ABT sessions, the difficulties in emotional regulation in clients reduce.

Table 1: Age wise Distribution

Age Group	No of Patients
21-30years	8
31-40 years	5
41-50 years	2
51-60 years	2
Total	17

Graph 1: Age wise Distribution

Table 2: Education

Education	No. of Patients
8	1
9	1
10	4
12	5
Did not complete graduation	3
Diploma	1
Graduate	2
Total	17

Graph 2: Education

Table 3: Occupation

Occupation	No. of Patients
Self Employed	7
Farming	3
Service	3
unemployed	4
Total	17

Table 4: Cause of absenteeism

Cause of Absenteeism	No. of patients reported
Alcohol	15
Cannabis	1
Sleeping Pills	1
Opioids	1
Gambling	1
MDMA	1

Table 5: Marital Status

Marital Status	No. of Patients
Single	7
Married	9
Divorced	1
Total	17

Graph 3: Marital status

Graph 5: Self-reported reasons for substance use or relapse

Graph 6: Self-reported Withdrawal Symptoms

Table 6: Stay in Rehab Centre

Stay in Rehab Centre (months)	Frequency
1	9
2	6
3	1
4	1
Total	17

Table 7: Rosenberg Self Esteem Score

	Mean Score BEFORE (SD)	Mean Score AFTER (SD)	't' statistic	p value
Rosenberg Self Esteem Score	9.18(3.1)	21.24(2.5)	-3.038	0.008

Discussion

Addictions to substances and behaviours have a big impact on the individual, his state of mind, as well as a bigger negative impact on the close family and community at large. This issue is relapsing in nature and is characterised by frequent relapses. This is frequently caused by a variety of reasons including biological features, personality traits, and socioeconomic and vocational considerations. Arts-based therapy is the application of art in a therapeutic setting to reach specific, individual aims (ABT) [12,13]. It is based on the Subtle Energy Guide (SEG), which integrates findings from studies in Indian psychology and ethics, human development, and cognitive neuroscience. ABT uses methods and draws inspiration from the dramatic, musical, and visual arts [14,15]. The arts as they are currently practised contribute to the therapeutic role in a number of ways, including creative skill, improvised painting and sculpture, the construction and dismantling of metaphoric meaning, and situations that are beyond the scope of language. This study was conducted to assess the effect of arts-based therapy on patients admitted to a facility for treating behavioural and drug addictions' self-esteem.

In this study changes in self-esteem and emotional control following 30 sessions of arts-based treatment over three months were examined in this study involving 17 individuals admitted to a rehabilitation facility for behavioural and substance addictions. The outcomes were contrasted with other socio-occupational statistics. The Rosenberg self-esteem measure scores were shown to have significantly improved following ABT sessions. Alcohol-related absenteeism and self-esteem ratings had a

strong negative connection, showing that absenteeism at work would decrease with higher self-esteem.

According to recent studies, using music therapy with hospitalised young patients provides them with a secure opportunity to internalise a positive self-image in addition to their patient status (O Callaghan, 2013) [26]. Finding of previous study that giving music therapy is connected with an increase in the proportion of adolescent patients getting rehabilitated shows how treatment facilities may be adjusting their adolescent community with a therapeutic approach that better meets their requirements (Vourakis, 2005) [27].

Since the 12-step programme has been associated with art and music therapy for many years, researchers have presumed that art therapy can complement and improve an existing effective form of treatment. Previous research revealed an association between the usage of both music therapy and art therapy and the requirement of 12-step meetings as part of treatment. This finding validates earlier research (Johnson, 1990) [24] linking the use of art and music therapy with a 12-step model, and it advises treatment facilities to keep combining these therapies with a 12-step strategy.

Previous investigations looked at how various types of psychosocial treatment relate to the usage of art and music therapy, and we discovered that there are diverse relationships between the two. An important finding for those who have suggested the clear connection between motivational enhancement therapy and the use of art therapy is that the usage of motivational enhancement therapy in substance use disorder treatment facilities was positively

connected to offering art therapy (Holt & Kaiser, 2009; Horay, 2006) [21,22].

Every element of the lives of persons who have addictions to substances or behaviours is significantly impacted. The nature of the problem is recurring. As a result, these people are usually accepted into rehab centres. They use marijuana, alcohol, and tobacco for recreational purposes. Typically, it begins with friends due to curiosity, experimentation, and peer pressure. These substances develop a tolerance with repeated use, which leads to dependency with increased frequency and dosage. Adverse life events frequently worsen substance use, which increases from irregular to frequent to harmful use. Later, individuals find it challenging to stop using these substances because of the unpleasant withdrawal symptoms that follow discontinuation [16-18].

Substance abuse enters their lives, which has a detrimental effect on their reputation, social life, finances, employment, and academic achievement. When someone tries to stop someone from using drugs, there is interpersonal conflict. To support their substance usage, they start to lie, spend irresponsibly, rack up debt, sell things, gamble, or steal; some may even find themselves in legal problems. Accidents involving intoxication occur often. Some drug users have behavioural problems that could lead to relationship problems. Substance abuse has a negative impact on every aspect of their lives, and they typically find it difficult to change this behaviour on their own [19-21].

Since the 1950s, art therapy has been used to treat substance use disorders. Art therapy can be used to treat addictions, according to the American Art Therapy Association (AATA) (American Art Therapy Association, 2014). The foundational tenet of art therapy is that the patient will be able to communicate nonverbally, imaginatively, and creatively. A

variety of activities are included in art therapy, such as incident drawings (a drawing of an incident that happened while using drugs or alcohol), drawing or painting emotions, stress painting (painting when anxious or stressed out in order to relieve those feelings), keeping an art journal, and making sculptures.

Most art therapy methods for people with SUDs involve a creative process in which the patient makes art, but some specialised applications also use the interpretation and meditation of well-known pieces of art.

Although the research designs prevent definitive generalisation, the advantages of art therapy have been the subject of extensive investigation. These findings point to a number of advantages for SUD patients, including a decrease in denial, a decrease in resistance to alcoholism treatment, a communication outlet, and a reduction in shame. By bringing people out of reflection and into a state of action, viewing, discussing, and understanding existing art can aid in group conversations and can inspire patients to make changes [22,23].

One technique to help someone get over their drug addiction and develop a healthy view and way of life is to admit and treat them in a rehabilitation clinic. It provides children with a safer environment to be in, free from drugs and others who use them. Through interesting group and one-on-one sessions, the rehabilitation center's programme participants can learn about the benefits of having regular waking and sleeping hours, exercise, regular meals, and introspection. Most patients join rehab centres with resentment, varying levels of motivation, and hostility due to pressure from family members [24-26].

Conclusion

Considering the improvements in the scores of self-esteem and emotional regulation, Arts Based Therapy could be used widely in the

treatment and rehabilitation of people having substance and behavioural addictions. There is need for more and more trainers in Arts Based Therapy so that this therapy can be available for more and more people.

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